

EVOLUTION OF CLASSICAL MANAGEMENT THEORIES

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Abstract: The article discusses the evolution of classical management theories, highlighting the historical context and the socioeconomic influences that shaped administrative practices over time. From the earliest civilizations, such as the Egyptians and Mesopotamians, to the Industrial Revolution, management underwent significant transformations. The revolution brought the need for new approaches, such as Scientific Management, proposed by Frederick Taylor, who introduced systematic methods to increase efficiency in factories. Standardization, division of labor, and the study of time and motion were essential to increase productivity and optimize administrative processes. The article also mentions the contribution of Henry Ford, who applied the principles of Scientific Management to mass production, consolidating the importance of management as a science.

Keywords: Industrial Revolution; Scientific Management; Efficiency and Productivity;

0. Introduction

This article is titled: Evolution of Classical Management Theories. It aims to explore the emergence and development of organizations, as well as the administrative process associated with them, and the influences related to each period of the schools that form the so-called classical approach to management. This work is of utmost importance because understanding the history of management, the types of management that exist, as well as their applications and results within organizations, leads to a greater understanding of management techniques and how to apply them in the modern world. The aim is, through bibliographical research, to investigate key authors of the main administrative theories.

It is important to emphasize that the evolution of management happened gradually and very slowly, and it has existed since ancient times, which is why Reinaldo da Silva affirms that:

"Although quite nebulous, management is an activity found in ventures of any kind, by all people, at all times. In fact, all the great leaders recorded in history were managers – managing countries, coordinating explorations, leading wars, managing the efforts of other men." (SILVA, 2008, p. 78)

The capitalist system arises with the decline of the feudal system, manufacturing, and guilds, followed by the rise of the bourgeoisie and the absolutist state. Organizations have existed since the beginning of social man, as organizations are dynamic and highly complex entities that can be conceptualized in various ways. The most common conceptualization is "An organization is defined as two or more people with the desire and willingness to cooperate to achieve a common goal" (MITROFF, 1994, p. 12).

With the Industrial Revolution of the 18th century, a new production model emerged along with several transformations in organizations. This is when the first management theories emerged: "Despite aspects of management from many years ago, no event had a greater impact on the study and practice of management than the Industrial Revolution" (SILVA, 2008, p. 93).

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1. The Principles of Management

1.1. Empirical Management and the First Practices

Management, as a practice, has existed since the earliest social organizations. Ancient civilizations, such as the Egyptians and Mesopotamians, demonstrated administrative skills when building large structures, such as the pyramids and ziggurats, which required planning, division of labor, and coordination. According to Chiavenato (2004, p. 15), "the history of management is as old as humanity itself, since the need for organization and coordination of efforts is intrinsic to life in society." The administrative systems of these civilizations were based on centralized leadership and rigid hierarchical structures. In the Babylonian and Egyptian empires, leaders delegated specific tasks to their subordinates, who carried them out by following strict standards. According to Weber (1999, p. 32), "administrative rationality could already be observed in primitive bureaucracy, even though it lacked formal concepts of efficiency."

Management was also crucial in the military context. The war strategies developed by the Romans exemplify how an efficient organization could determine success. Generals distributed responsibilities among centurions and used effective communication methods to coordinate the troops (CHIAVENATO, 2004).

1.2. Industrial Revolution and the Emergence of Scientific Management

The Industrial Revolution marked a break with traditional practices, introducing the need for more systematic management. The transition from a craft-based model to mass production generated challenges such as standardization, quality control, and worker motivation. According to Drucker (2002, p. 87), "the Industrial Revolution not only transformed the means of production but also introduced the complexity that required new forms of management." With the rise of factories, direct supervision and performance measurement became indispensable. In this context, ideas emerged that directly influenced the foundations of scientific management, such as Adam Smith's studies on the division of labor.

This is an example of a quote.

2. Administratio classics theorys

The world entered the industrial age from the late 18th and early 19th centuries, a milestone that represented a significant transition from the predominantly agricultural and artisanal period that had been in place until then. This new industrial context was characterized by a revolution in production processes, with the introduction of machines and new technologies that transformed the way goods and services were produced. Economies began to depend more on industry than on agriculture, and social and economic structures changed profoundly. The countries that managed to industrialize quickly, such as the United States, the United Kingdom, and Germany, became known as "industrialized countries" and soon stood out on the global stage, rising as economic powers. These countries, with their expanding industries, came to be known as first-world nations, as they dominated large-scale production, controlled global trade and the world economy, and displayed high levels of urbanization and technological development. The constant growth of factories and the expansion of large corporations reflected a new era of economic prosperity, but also presented challenges, such as efficient management of resources and workers.

It was in this context that, in the early 20th century, two engineers stood out by conducting the first systematic studies on management, aiming to organize and optimize production and management processes. Frederick Winslow Taylor, an American engineer, founded the School of Scientific Management, an approach that focused on improving industrial efficiency. Taylor believed that productivity could be increased through the rationalization of labor, meaning by carefully analyzing the tasks performed by workers. He proposed systematic methods to study and optimize each movement of workers, ensuring greater productivity and efficiency. This innovative approach profoundly influenced industrial management, especially in the context of factory expansion.

2.1. Taylor's Scientific Management The School of Scientific Management brings administration as a science, transforming the natural and uncoordinated process of management into a system of organized and systematic knowledge, obtained through specific methods and techniques aimed at explaining, understanding, and predicting natural, social, or artificial phenomena. The entire School of Scientific Management emphasized tasks.

"The name Scientific Management refers to the attempt to apply the methods of science to management problems in order to increase industrial efficiency. The main scientific methods applicable to management problems are observation and measurement" (CHIAVENATO, 2014, p.56).

The School of Scientific Management was initiated in the early 20th century by American engineer Frederick W. Taylor, considered the pioneer of modern General Management Theory (GMT). Taylor had several followers (such as Gantt, Gilbreth, Emerson, Ford, Barth, among others) and caused a true transformation in administrative thought and in the industrial sector of his time. The initial focus was on eliminating waste and losses in industries, seeking to increase productivity through the application of methods and techniques from industrial engineering.

"Frederick Winslow Taylor (1856-1915), the founder of Scientific Management, was born in Philadelphia, United States. He came from a Quaker family with rigid principles and was educated with a strong mindset of discipline, devotion to work, and savings. He began his career as a worker at Midvale Steel Co., moving up from foreman to assistant manager, eventually becoming an engineer after graduating from the Stevens Institute. At that time, the system of payment by piece or task was in place. Employers sought to maximize profits by setting the task price, while workers slowed down their production to counterbalance the piece rate set by employers. This led Taylor to study the production problem in search of a solution that would meet the needs of both employers and employees" (CHIAVENATO, 2014, p.57).

Taylor's first period coincides with the publication of his book *Shop Management* (1903), in which he addressed techniques for rationalizing workers' tasks through the study of time and motion. Taylor began his analysis from the ground up, directly observing workers in their executive roles, conducting detailed work by examining the tasks of each worker, breaking down their movements and processes to improve and make them more efficient. He realized that the average worker, with the available equipment, produced far less than what they were capable of. He also found that when the most efficient worker saw they were paid the same as the least productive worker, they tended to become complacent, losing interest and not reaching their full potential. This led Taylor to conclude that conditions should be created to pay more to the more productive workers.

Essentially, Taylor stated in *Shop Management* that the goal of management is to improve wages and reduce unit production costs. To achieve this, management must apply scientific methods of research and experimentation to develop principles and establish standardized processes that allow for the control of factory operations. Workers should be scientifically selected and positioned in their roles with the proper conditions to ensure that standards are met. They must also be scientifically trained to improve their skills and carry out tasks in a way that meets production goals. Furthermore, management must create an environment of close and cordial cooperation with workers in order to maintain a psychological climate favorable to productivity. Taylor's time and motion study led to many other studies, which is why it is stated that "Efficient management of people and resources became imperative on the production lines, especially when time and motion began to be analyzed scientifically" (DRUCKER, 2002, p. 90).

Taylor's second period is marked by the publication of his book *The Principles of Scientific Management* (1911), where he concluded that rationalizing workers' tasks needed to be accompanied by a general organizational structure within the company to ensure the consistent application of his principles throughout the organization. From there, Taylor expanded his studies to general management, creating Scientific Management while continuing his concern with workers' tasks. He identified that the industries of his time faced

significant challenges that needed to be addressed through the application of scientific methods. Among the main problems Taylor pointed out were workers' systematic loafing, which reduced production to about one-third of what would be considered normal, due to the belief that higher productivity would lead to unemployment, inadequate management that encouraged idleness to protect workers' personal interests, and the use of ineffective empirical methods. Other problems included managers' ignorance of work routines and the time required to complete them, as well as the lack of uniformity in work techniques and methods, which hindered standardization and reduced operational efficiency.

"Taylor found that workers learned how to perform tasks by observing their fellow workers. This led to different methods of performing the same task and a great variety of different tools and instruments for each operation. Since there is always a faster method and more suitable instrument, these methods and tools can be found and refined through scientific analysis and a careful study of time and motion, rather than relying on the personal discretion of each worker. This attempt to replace empirical and rudimentary methods with scientific methods was called Rational Organization of Work (ROW)" (CHIAVENATO, 2014, p.59).

The ROW or Rational Organization of Work proposed by Taylor starts with the study of Time and Motion. In this sense, after Taylor observed that there was a lot of standardization, inefficiency, and lack of coordination in the tasks being performed (i.e., people with the same position and function did the work differently and took more or less time than their colleagues), through scientific analysis, Taylor deduced that there was a worker who performed the tasks more efficiently and this worker became the paradigm, or the model to be followed by others. He also noticed that the ideal situation would be to divide the work and have each task divided into specific sub-tasks, with one worker specializing in each task, leading to standardization.

The ROW (Rational Organization of Work) is based on the following aspects:

Work analysis and time and motion study: Work analysis, one of the pillars of Scientific Management, involves breaking tasks down into their simplest steps to determine the most efficient way to perform them. This approach aims to eliminate unnecessary movements and reduce waste. Study of human fatigue: The study of human fatigue recognizes the impact of physical and mental effort on workers' performance. This principle highlights that scheduled breaks, proper intervals, and comfortable working environments are essential for productivity. Division of labor and worker specialization: The division of labor, proposed by Taylor, consists of breaking organizational activities into specific tasks and assigning them to specialized workers. Job and task design: Job and task design is the detailing of the functions each employee should perform, including the methods and tools used. Salary incentives and production rewards: Scientific Management emphasizes the use of financial incentives as a way to motivate workers to achieve higher productivity levels. Concept of homo economicus: The concept of homo economicus is based on the idea that humans are driven by the rational pursuit of maximizing economic gains. Working conditions: The influence of the work environment on productivity is a central principle in Scientific Management. Factors such as lighting, ventilation, temperature, and noise were studied to create optimal conditions for workers' performance. Standardization: Standardization is the uniformity of methods, tools, and work processes to reduce variation and ensure consistency in results. Taylor argued that standardization promoted predictability and efficiency. This principle is widely applied in mass production, such as in the assembly line model introduced by Henry Ford.

3. Conclusions

Therefore, we can observe that the evolution of classical management theories reflects a gradual adaptation to social and economic changes, particularly with the advent of the Industrial Revolution. The first administrative practices emerged in ancient civilizations and evolved with the need for greater organization and productivity in industries. Scientific Management, proposed by Frederick Taylor, was crucial in transforming management

into a science, focusing on efficiency, standardization, and specialization of labor. These principles, in addition to influencing industrial organizations, remain fundamental in modern management.

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